

Exploring the Impacts of Experimental Floods on Riparian Vegetation in the Lower Spöl River (Swiss Alps): Insights from Remote Sensing- and Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle- (UAV-) Based Monitoring

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Abstract: This work aims to investigate the short- and long-term effects of experimental floods (i.e., high flows released from a dam for river restoration purposes) on riparian vegetation in a regulated alpine river. The study uses RGB orthoimages from UAV (2018-2023) and historical aerial imagery (2006-2022) to characterise riparian vegetation composition and mortality in the Spöl River (Swiss Alps). Riparian tree stands were digitised based on a field survey, where the species composition was recorded along with the proportion of dead or dying trees. The orthoimages were used to compute an index based on the red and blue bands (KANA index), and non-parametric zonal statistics were applied to each riparian tree stand. The performance of this index varied substantially across datasets: it is likely that image acquisition conditions and sensor characteristics exerted a strong influence on index values and comparability. However, in recent UAV-derived images, results showed that KANA could effectively discriminate between 1. vegetation types, with broadleaved stands exhibiting higher values than coniferous stands, and 2. levels of mortality, with decreasing values corresponding to increased proportions of dead trees in the stand. Historical aerial imagery proved unsuitable for applying KANA to characterise vegetation. It appears, however, that in suitable conditions, KANA can be a useful alternative to vegetation indices such as NDVI if near-infrared data are unavailable. Furthermore, RGB-based analyses allow to examine a considerably larger corpus of data than multispectral analyses. We therefore recommend further exploring possible applications and limitations of this index for cost-effective assessment of riparian vegetation composition and health conditions.

Keywords: vegetation index; RGB imagery; UAV/UAS; riparian vegetation.

1 Introduction

Vegetation monitoring from aerial or satellite imagery often applies arithmetic operations to the raw sensor data to facilitate vegetation differentiation and extract information about vegetation health and composition (e.g. Huang et al. 2021). These images' band transformations are termed vegetation indices (VIs).

One of the best-known VIs nowadays, the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), was suggested by Krieglner et al. (1969) and uses the near infrared (NIR) and red (R) bands, according to the equation (1).

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-R}{NIR+R} \quad (1)$$

Ongoing developments in optical sensors and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) have increased the accessibility of high-resolution multispectral imaging, further popularising NDVI (e.g. Ma et al. 2022). However, the calibration of different sensors for multispectral imagery is complex and error-prone (Huang et al. 2021). Radiometric and geometric calibration is also required in the visible spectrum (red, green and blue bands, RGB), but processing is generally easier than for NIR data (Ma et al. 2022). This has led to the development of VIs based solely on visible bands. One of these is KANA (2), (acronym suggested by Roncoroni et al. 2022 after Kawashima and Nakatani, 1998). Roncoroni et al. (2022) showed that this VI is appropriate to extract periphyton from river orthomosaics and suggested it may be more robust to variable lighting than other VIs.

$$KANA = \frac{R-B}{R+B} \quad (2)$$

In the case of long-term monitoring, such as in the study of vegetation succession patterns, RGB-based VIs have the potential to greatly expand the corpus of historical data. This study hypothesised that the KANA index could prove suitable for differentiating vegetation on historical imagery, owing to its relatively low sensitivity to different lighting conditions. KANA was computed from a set of pre-existing orthoimages to assess the suitability of the index to various sensor characteristics and lighting conditions. Accordingly, this study addressed two questions: (i) whether tree stand-level KANA values discriminate vegetation type and mortality class in a recent RGB orthoimage, and (ii) whether these values remain comparable across multi-date UAV and airborne imagery for long-term riparian vegetation monitoring.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

This study focuses on a 1.5 km long reach of the lower Spöl, a fifth-order stream near Zerne in the Eastern Swiss Alps (Figure 1a). The area of interest ranges from 1'507 m a.s.l. to 1'470 m a.s.l and is located on the border of the Swiss National Park (SNP). In the riparian corridor, vegetation is mainly restricted to the shrub and tree stratum, with little development of lower vegetation. The dominant species are *Alnus incana* L., *Salix spp.*, *Picea abies* L. and *Larix decidua* Mill. (O'Callaghan et al. 2025).

Figure 1. a) Location of the study area within Switzerland. b) Summary of the orthoimages used in this study. Aeroplane images are SWISSIMAGE datasets. (Swisstopo, 2022). Where not specified, UAV images are produced by the SNP.

The Spöl is regulated by two dams since 1970 and has been subjected to annual experimental floods since 2000. The effects of this programme on channel morphology and aquatic ecology in the lower Spöl have been the subject of several studies (e.g. Mathers et al. 2021), although its long-term effects on riparian vegetation have first been assessed recently (O’Callaghan et al. 2025).

2.2 Tree stratum relevé and analysis

A field survey of the tree stratum within the fluvial corridor (tree height ≥ 1.5 m, but including well-developed shrubs) was conducted in the summer of 2023 (O’Callaghan et al. 2025). One hundred and fifty-six stands (3.5-759 m², median 75.1 m²), i.e. contiguous groups of trees

characterised by homogeneity in species composition (presence only), tree size, density, and deadwood proportion, were identified and located on a map. Species composition was aggregated into three types: *broadleaved*, *coniferous*, and *mixed* (Figure 2b). A mortality class was recorded for each stand, with values 1: <25% of dead trees, 2: 25 – 75%, and 3: >75% (Figure 2c). These data were digitised in QGIS 3.28 (QGIS Development Team, 2022), using the 2023-06-16 SNP orthophoto as a basemap: each tree stand was delineated as a polygon corresponding to the extent of its canopy.

Figure 2. a) 2023-06-16 orthoimage of the study reach, resampled at 25 cm. b) Vegetation type and c) mortality class by stand, from the field survey by O’Callaghan et al. (2025). d) KANA index derived from (a). Note the scale capped at [-0.4, 0.4]. e) KANA values in 1 million randomly sampled pixels.

Table 1. Summary of criteria, data and statistical tests used in this study.

Criterion	Data	Data	Test
Differentiation between vegetation types	2023-06-16 dataset: Median KANA per stand, grouped by vegetation type	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Two-sided Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction
Differentiation between mortality classes	2023-06-16 dataset: Median KANA per stand, grouped by mortality class	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Two-sided Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction
Stability across datasets	All datasets: Median KANA per stand, filtered for mortality class 1 to mitigate fitness variability	Friedman test	Nemenyi's all-pairs comparison test
	All datasets: Median KANA per stand	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Two-sided Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction

2.3 Imagery and KANA index computation

UAV-borne RGB orthoimages are produced by the SNP and other research institutions (Zurich and Bern Universities of Applied Sciences, ZHAW and BFH, respectively) to monitor experimental floods since 2018. This study used eight of these datasets, as well as four airborne orthoimages from the national SWISSIMAGE series (Swisstopo, 2022, see Figure 1b). No information about the sensors or radiometric conditions was retrieved for these orthoimages.

KANA was computed in Manifold GIS 9 (Manifold Software 2023). For computational efficiency, all orthoimages were resampled to 25 cm. This coarsening is also expected to smoothen extreme values in individual pixels, and, therefore, provide a clearer signal of overall tree health. The KANA datasets were imported into QGIS, where the median values per tree stand were extracted. The rationale for selecting the median over individual pixel values was 1. to remove variability due to exposed sediment and individual variability between trees and 2. to aggregate KANA at the tree stand scale, in line with the mortality class and vegetation type.

Table 1 shows the steps applied to assess KANA usability to discriminate between vegetation types, mortality classes, and its stability across the different datasets. All statistical operations were performed in R v. 4.2.2 (R Core Team 2022).

3 Results

3.1 KANA vegetation index performance on the 2023 orthoimage

The histogram of KANA values computed on the resampled 2023-06-16 SNP orthoimage (Figure 3e) shows two peaks, one in the negative values near zero, and the other in the positive values. When compared with the orthoimage in Figure 3a, Figure 3d shows that the former generally corresponds to water and sediment, while the latter seems to correspond largely to vegetation. KANA differed significantly between all mortality classes ($H(2, n = 156) = 62.01, p < 0.01$ from a Kruskal-Wallis test, $p \leq 0.03$ on post-hoc Dunn's tests).

KANA rank sums also differed significantly between most vegetation types ($H(2, n = 156) = 20.89, p < 0.01$), with only the stands characterized with coniferous/mixed vegetation not showing significant differences. When filtering the stands to retain only the fittest vegetation (mortality class 1, as shown in Figure 3b), KANA values differed significantly between all categories (Dunn's test, $p \leq 0.03$).

Figure 3. 2023 tree stand median KANA values by (a) mortality class (* proportion of dead trees in the stand) and (b) by vegetation type in the fittest stands (mortality class 1).

3.2 KANA index performance on other datasets

Median KANA values per tree stand, filtered for mortality class 1 showed significant differences between datasets ($\chi^2(11) = 638.56, p < 0.01$, Friedman test). A post-hoc Nemenyi test showed that most datasets had significantly different values from each other. Compared with the 2023-06-16 dataset examined above, only the 2019-06-18, 2019-06-20, 2021-06-21 and 2022-06-25 datasets did not show statistically significant differences.

Both UAV-based and SWISSIMAGE datasets showed significant differences in KANA values between vegetation types (UAV: $H(2, n = 616) = 6.29, p = 0.04$, SWISSIMAGE: $H(2, n = 308) = 14.34, p < 0.01$). In both cases, the coniferous/mixed differences were not significant, but broadleaved stands differed significantly from both other types (Dunn's test $p \leq 0.04$). Strikingly, z-scores for the SWISSIMAGE datasets had comparable magnitudes to UAV datasets, but opposite signs, such that coniferous stands generally had the lowest values, while broadleaved stands had the highest.

Figure 4. Examples of different KANA values across datasets in an area with relatively stable vegetation. The 2022 and 2006 images are from SWISSIMAGE, all others from the SNP.

Figure 4 visually showcases the variability of KANA across datasets, despite this apparently robust differentiation between vegetation types.

4 Discussion

4.1 KANA index performance across datasets

The 2023-06-16 image were suitable for the implementation of KANA, as it was possible to discriminate clearly between vegetated and non-vegetated areas (Figure 2), but also between vegetation types and stand mortality levels (Figure 3). Interpretation should remain cautious, as the strength of group separation was not uniform across all categories and the relatively small sample sizes may affect significance. These results suggest that stand health condition must be considered when applying KANA, as it may affect vegetation type identification. This is in line with the reported correlation between this index and chlorophyll content (Kawashima and Nakatani 1998). Future research may investigate the effects of different image resolutions and KANA aggregation levels on its values and their interpretation.

Tests on other images show that KANA is sensitive to shadow effects (see Figure 4, particularly in the 2019-06-25 dataset). This may be mitigated by selecting images produced under more diffuse lighting conditions. Overall, in UAV-based datasets, KANA values remain in line with theoretical expectations (positive values associated with live vegetation only, Kawashima and Nakatani 1998). However, KANA appears sensitive to sensor characteristics when they affect coloration, as can be seen e.g. with the SWISSIMAGE datasets. In these datasets, values remained significantly different between vegetation types, despite the fact that the relative pattern was nearly inverse to that

observed in the UAV datasets. Radiometric normalisation, for example using pseudo-invariant features (Bao et al. 2012), may help reduce sensor differences and improve comparability across different datasets.

KANA can provide a considerable amount of within-image information about vegetation composition and health condition, even without any pre-processing. However, the inconsistencies observed between datasets indicate that raw KANA values cannot be directly interpreted across heterogeneous image series. Future work may investigate whether normalisation methods can improve inter-dataset consistency sufficiently to support the use of KANA for long-term monitoring based on historical imagery.

5 Conclusions

This study investigated an RGB-based vegetation index, which yielded promising results for the identification of vegetation type and health condition on the most recent UAV-based images. However, results were not sufficiently consistent across heterogeneous datasets to support robust interpretation of historical airborne imagery, likely because of large amounts of shading and variable sensor quality. We recommend further investigation of this index and the pre-processing it requires for use with historical datasets, as it appears to have considerable potential for vegetation monitoring in cases where multispectral indices are not applicable.

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6 References

- Bao, N., Lechner, A. M., Fletcher, A., Mellor, A., Mulligan, D., Bai, Z., 2012. Comparison of relative radiometric normalization methods using pseudo-invariant features for change detection studies in rural and urban landscapes. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 6(1), 063578–1.
- Huang, S., Tang, L., Hupy, J. P., Wang, Y., Shao, G., 2021. A commentary review on the use of normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) in the era of popular remote sensing. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 32(1), 1–6.
- Kawashima, S., Nakatani, M., 1998. An Algorithm for Estimating Chlorophyll Content in Leaves Using a Video Camera. *Annals of Botany*, 81(1), 49–54.
- Kriegler, F. J., Malila, W. A., Nalepka, R. F., Richardson, W., 1969. Preprocessing Transformations and Their Effects on Multispectral Recognition. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, VI, 97.
- Ma, Y., Ma, L., Zhang, Q., Huang, C., Yi, X., Chen, X., Hou, T., Lv, X., Zhang, Z., 2022. Cotton Yield Estimation Based on Vegetation Indices and Texture Features Derived From RGB Image. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 925986.
- Manifold Software, 2023. Manifold Release 9 Professional. <https://manifold.net/>. (Accessed 1 April 2026).
- Mathers, K. L., Robinson, C. T., Weber, C., 2021. Artificial flood reduces fine sediment clogging enhancing hyporheic zone physicochemistry and accessibility for macroinvertebrates. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence*, 2(4).
- O’Callaghan, M., del Hoyo, J. G., Finch, B. D., Ruiz-Villanueva, V., 2026. Grow With the Flow? Impact of Experimental Floods on Riparian Vegetation in an Alpine River. *River Research and Applications*, 42(1), 162–175.
- QGIS Development Team., 2022. QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. <https://www.qgis.org>. (Accessed 1 April 2026).
- R Core Team, 2022. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/> (Accessed 1 April 2026).
- Roncoroni, M., Mancini, D., Kohler, T. J., Miesen, F., Gianini, M., Battin, T. J., N. Lane, S., 2022. Centimeter-scale mapping of phototrophic biofilms in glacial forefields using visible band ratios and UAV imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 43(13), 4723–4757.
- Swisstopo, 2022. SWISSIMAGE Orthoimage series. Federal Office of Topography. (Accessed 1 April 2026).